

Polarographic Study of Thallium (I) Complexes of 2,2'-Dimercapto Diethyl Ether

R. S. SAXENA and S. S. SHEELWANT

Department of Chemistry, Malaviya Regional Engineering College, Jaipur

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The complexation between Tl(I) and 2,2'-dimercapto diethyl ether has been studied polarographically in 40% ethanolic media. The reduction of the complexes is found to be reversible and diffusion controlled for one electron transfer process. DeFord and Hume's method revealed the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes whose stabilities and degree of formation have been determined at 20° and 30°. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have also been reported.

IN continuation of our work on the polarographic study of mercapto compounds and their metal complexes¹⁻⁵, this paper reports the determination of the composition, stability constants and degree of formation of Tl⁺ complexes of 2,2' dimercapto diethyl ether at different temperatures by polarographic method of DeFord and Hume. The values of change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for the complexation reaction have also been calculated. There is, however, no reference in the literature on the present work.

Experimental

2,2'-dimercapto diethyl ether, referred herein as R(SH)₂, was supplied by Evan's chemetics Inc., N.Y. and all other chemicals were of Anal-R (BDH) grade. The entire study was carried out in 40% ethanol and at pH 3.8 maintained by ammonium acetate-acetic acid buffer using NaClO₄ as supporting electrolyte and Triton X-100 as maximum suppressor.

A manual polarograph and scalamp galvanometer were employed for recording the polarograms using S.C.E. as the reference electrode. The capillary used had the following characteristics: $m = 2.652 \text{ mg/sec}$, $t = 2.65 \text{ sec}$ and $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.253 \text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{t}^{-1/2}$ in a

solution containing 40% ethanol and 0.1 M NaClO₄. The temperature was controlled by the Universal thermostat U₃ type (Germany). For determining the composition and stabilities of the complexes the solutions containing 1.0 mM TlNO₃ + 0.1 M NaClO₄ + 0.002% Triton X-100 and varying amount of R(SH)₂ (0.00 - 0.14 M) were polarographed at 20° and 30°. The solutions were deaerated with nitrogen for 15-20 min before the polarograms were recorded and the inert atmosphere was maintained above the solution during the electrolysis.

Results and Discussion

The conventional log plots for the polarograms of Tl⁺ in absence and presence of R(SH)₂ at pH 3.8 were found to be straight lines whose slopes were in agreement with the theoretical value for one electron transfer process indicating the reversibility of the electrode reaction. The diffusion-controlled nature of the wave height was shown by the linear plot of i_d vs. $h_{\text{eff}}^{1/2}$ and the constant values of $i_d/h_{\text{eff}}^{1/2}$ determined at various heights of mercury column. With increase in R(SH)₂-concentration, the shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential and decrease in i_d (Table 1) indicated the complex formation between metal ions and the ligand⁶.

TABLE 1—THE VALUES OF P_d , $E_{1/2}$ AND 30° AND VARIOUS FUNCTIONS AT 20° and 30°

[X] (M)	$i_d (\mu)$		$-E_{1/2}(\text{V})$		Fo(X)		F ₁ (X)		F ₂ (X)	
	20°	30°	20°	30°	20°	30°	20°	30°	20°	30°
0.00	6.40	7.65	0.417	0.417	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.02	5.64	6.88	0.425	0.424	1.558	1.454	—	—	—	—
0.04	5.60	6.84	0.432	0.431	2.071	1.913	26.8	22.82	170	133
0.06	5.57	6.80	0.440	0.438	2.860	2.517	31.0	25.28	183	130
0.08	5.54	6.78	0.446	0.444	3.649	3.177	33.1	27.21	164	121
0.10	5.50	6.73	0.452	0.450	4.661	4.028	36.6	30.28	166	128
0.14	5.35	6.63	0.462	0.460	7.132	6.000	43.8	35.70	170	130

The plot of $E_{1/2}$ as a function of \log [ligand] showed a curvature (Fig. 1) expected for the formation of successive complexes and hence DeFord and Hume's method⁷ has been applied for determining the composition and stability constants of the complexes which have been related to the polarographic data by a series of equations. If a single complex had been formed the plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs. \log [ligand] would have been a straight line and given sufficient information about the complex. For the reversible reduction of a complexed metal ion to the metal amalgam.

Fig. 1—Plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs. \log [ligand] at 20°.

DeFord and Hume have, under the condition of constant ionic strength defined the functions, $F_j(X)$ such as

$$F_0(X) = \text{antilog} \left[0.435 \frac{nF}{RT} \left\{ (E_{1/2})_s - (E_{1/2})_o \right\} + \log \frac{I_s}{I_o} \right]$$

$$= \beta_0 + \beta_1(X) + \beta_2(X)^2 + \dots + \beta_N(X)^N \quad (1)$$

$$F_1(X) = \frac{F_0(X) - \beta_0}{(X)} = \beta_1 + \beta_2(X) + \beta_3(X)^2 + \dots + \beta_N(X)^{N-1} \quad (2)$$

$$F_2(X) = \frac{F_1(X) - \beta_1}{(X)} = \beta_2 + \beta_3(X) + \dots + \beta_N(X)^{N-2} \quad (3)$$

and so on. β_0 is the stability constant of the zero complex which is equal to unity. $(E_{1/2})_s$ and $(E_{1/2})_o$ are half wave potentials for the uncomplexed and complexed metal ions respectively; I_s and I_o are the respective values of diffusion current constant.

The values of various functions were plotted against [ligand] as shown in Fig. 2. The plot of $F_2(x)$ gave a horizontal straight line indicating that only two complexes were formed. From the extrapolation of these curves to $[X]=0$, as devised by Ledén⁸, the values of β_1 and β_2 were obtained from the intercept on the $F_j(X)$ axis and are given below :

Fig. 2—Plots of $F_j(X)$ vs. [ligand] at 20°.

$$\beta_1 = 20, \beta_2 = 170 \text{ at } 20^\circ$$

$$\text{and } \beta_1 = 17.5, \beta_2 = 130 \text{ at } 30^\circ$$

The degree of formation of the j^{th} complex, a_j is given by

$$a_j = \frac{(MX_j)}{[M]} = \frac{\beta_j(X)^j}{F_0(X)} \quad \dots (4)$$

from which the values of a_0 , a_1 and a_2 were calculated and the distribution curves, for the various complex species obtained by plotting these values against \log [ligand] are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3—Distribution curves for various complexes at 20°.

Thermodynamic Functions : The values of overall change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for the complexation reaction determined at 30° from the relations :

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta_2 \quad (5)$$

$$\log \beta_2 - \log \beta_1 = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303R} \left[\frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 T_2} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T} \quad (7)$$

are found to be -2.92 Kcal/mole, -4.76 Kcal/mole and -6.07 cal/mole degree respectively.

References

1. R. S. SAXENA and K. C. GUPTA., *Canad. J. Chem* , 1968, **46**, 311.
2. R. S. SAXENA and U. S. CHATURVEDI., *Electrochim Acta*, 1971, **16**, 1107 and 1972, **17**, 2009.
3. R. S. SAXENA and U. S. CHATURVEDI., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 3597.
4. R. S. SAXENA and S. S. SHEELWANT., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 43.
5. R. S. SAXENA and S. S. SHEELWANT., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 941.
6. D. R. CROW., "Polarography of Metal complexes", Academic Press, New York, 1969, p. 56.
7. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME., *J. Amer Chem Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5321.
8. I. LEDEN., *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, **188**, 160.